

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

STEPS OF REPUBLIK AZERBAIJAN OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

The socio-economic policy of the Republic of Azerbaijan, ensuring dynamic development in all spheres, also contributes to the development of communication and information technologies. World experience confirms that the use of ICT serves the comprehensive development of the country and is one of the important tools for solving socio-economic problems of the population. In recent years, positive steps have been taken in the Republic of Azerbaijan and valuable achievements have been achieved in the use of information and communication technologies. The development of the ICT sector, cooperation with leading countries in this area is considered one of the priorities of state policy. International cooperation in the field of ICT is carried out in the conditions of a cross-country struggle for the possession of technology and information resources, the creation of its own information coverage. Cooperation with the Republic of Belarus, which has risen to the level of a strategic partner of Azerbaijan, is of particular importance in this area. The Republic of Belarus, located at the intersection of the information flows of the European continent, is actively developing its information infrastructure, successfully using its advantageous geographical location. The digital transformation of the economy and the widespread introduction of innovations are among the factors that ensure the sustainable development of the country. The Republic of Belarus, which is one of the world's leading countries in the field of ICT, has an active international scientific and technical cooperation with a number of foreign countries, and has many scientific and technical projects. The Republic of Azerbaijan is also notable for its special attention to international cooperation in the field of information and communication technologies and has ties with a number of influential associations. Cooperation in the field of ICT between Azerbaijan and Belarus, which have close cooperation in various sectors of the economy, supporting each other in the international arena, has very prospects and is in the sphere of interests of both countries. Since 2010, the regular organization of Azerbaijani-Belarusian business forums in the field of information and communication technologies has further strengthened cooperation in the field of high technologies.

Keywords: information technologies, technology parks, cooperation in the field of ICT, Azerbaijani-Belarusian relations, the fight against cybercrime

Introductions: The creation of an information society in Azerbaijan in the XXI century is proof that the sphere of information and communication technologies occupies a key place after the oil industry. It is an indisputable fact that the importance of ICT at present and in the future will appear in the foreground, will give a powerful impetus to the comprehensive development of the country. Interest in the development of this sphere in Azerbaijan is reflected in the country's foreign economic policy, and cooperation with Belarus, which has achieved success in the field of ICT, is of particular importance.

At the end of the XX-beginning of the XXI century, deeply introducing information and communication technologies (ICT) into all spheres of public life determine the development of the world economy. In the context of the globalization of the world economy, the development of information and communication technologies is one of the most important components of the sustainable economic development of the state, as well as one of the main needs for improving the quality of life of citizens. Therefore, national programs aimed at the formation and development of the foundations of the information society are being developed and implemented in different countries, national systems of "electronic government" are being created. The

creation and functioning of an appropriate infrastructure of information technologies and communications, the improvement of computer literacy of the population, Internet access contribute to the development of electronic business and commerce, the infrastructure of public electronic services is provided.

The importance of information technology is evidenced by the expansion of scientific research in this area, the constant relevance of the production and sale of electronic computing equipment, as well as the growing demand for services in the field of information technology. All this especially emphasizes international cooperation in a number of innovative areas, relations in this area are becoming more complex, and therefore new scientific and economic events are regularly held. In world practice, the term "international innovation and technological cooperation" is used to explain the processes of cooperation and cooperation in higher scientific fields. This type of international relations is divided into bilateral and multilateral, reflecting international scientific and technical, innovative, production and marketing activities. The socio-economic policy in the Republic of Azerbaijan, aimed at ensuring dynamic development in all spheres, also contributes to the development of communication and information technology. This is evidenced by the adoption by the

leadership of the state of a number of orders in the field of ICT. International cooperation and the creation of the Republic of Azerbaijan's own information space in the field of ICT is accompanied in the context of competition between countries. Cooperation with the Republic of Belarus, which has risen to the level of a strategic partner of Azerbaijan, is of particular importance in this area. Interstate meetings at various levels with the Republic of Azerbaijan, with which the Republic of Belarus has close bilateral ties, long-term political dialogues have positively influenced the intensive development of inter-republican cooperation [6, p. 8]. In the field of ICT, one of the leading countries is the Republic of Belarus, which carries out active international scientific and technical cooperation with a number of foreign countries. A noticeable increase in the number of scientific and technical projects in which Belarus participates under international agreements, the creation and continuation of cooperation with various countries of the world, as well as with the UN Economic Commission, confirm the rapid progress of Belarus in the field of information and communication technologies. In recent years, the number of joint scientific and technical projects of the Republic of Belarus has significantly increased within the framework of international agreements, since 2016 joint projects have been launched with Azerbaijan, Cuba, Mongolia, Pakistan, Slovakia and Uzbekistan [8].

Results and discussion Integration trends in various regions of the world have become a normal process of human development. The participation of countries in integration, regardless of the level of development, cultural, religious and historical traditions, also affects the prevention of a number of problems, both in regions and throughout the world [7, p. 46]. The integration of the CIS countries reflects different formats, with different levels. The development of countries is largely determined by the level of international economic relations, the increase in mutual export-import, direct investment, and all this increases the efficiency of public production [7, p. 28; 5].

The Azerbaijan Republic is particularly attention to international cooperation in the field of information and communication technologies. In this regard, Azerbaijan has connections with a number of authoritative associations, among which specialized organizations (the International Electric Union, World Postal Union, regional cooperation in the field of communications) occupy an important place. Creation of the European Commission for Adaptation to Digital Markets in the framework of "Economic integration and adaptation to the European Union policy" was an important step towards strengthening the cooperation of European countries in this area. On November 18-19, 2015, the first meeting of the participants of the discussion took place in Brussels. Events for 2016-2017 within the framework of the "adaptation of digital markets", Azerbaijan was selected from among the participants of the Eastern Cooperation Program and announced jointly with Belarus as the main performer in the field of electronic customs, as well as in the field of medium and small electronic entrepreneurship. In addition, the action plan included the project "Creation of a regional network of

cooperation between technology parks focused on ICT", proposed by the Ministry of High Technologies and Communications [9; 2].

On November 11-12, 2012, the first meeting of the Ministers of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) was held in Tehran. Representatives of the Republic of Azerbaijan took part in the event at which the Tehran Declaration was adopted. The next meeting of the organization was held on December 5, 2017 in Baku. The Baku Declaration on the issues discussed by the working groups was adopted here, and it was noted that the discussions will contribute to the development of ICT in the OECD member countries [9].

Azerbaijan and Belarus support each other in the international arena and have close relationships in various sectors of the economy. Cooperation in the field of ICT between Azerbaijan and Belarus also promises great prospects and meets the interests of both countries. The first Azerbaijani-Belarusian business forum in the field of information and communication technologies was held in February 2010. A number of documents aimed at strengthening and developing cooperation between the countries in the field of high technologies were signed at the event in Baku. It should be noted that the foundation for the event was laid two years ago. In March 2008, when the Minister of Communications and Information Technologies of Azerbaijan Ali Abbasov was on a working visit to Belarus, a unanimous opinion was reached on the need to exchange experience between the countries in the field of software and identify ways to develop cooperation. In November of the same year, at the XIV International Exhibition BakuTel 2008, a plan of cooperation in the field of ICT was developed between the two countries, signed by the Deputy Ministers of Communications [3]. The mentioned forum in the field of ICT can be called a productive event in solving the issues raised. The forum was prepared by the Ministry of Communications and Information Technologies of Azerbaijan, the Embassy of the Republic of Belarus in Azerbaijan with the participation of the Hi-Tech Park (HTP). Within the framework of the forum, HTP residents presented their products in four areas: solutions for the banking sector, communications and telecommunications, information society, information projects for the oil and gas industry. The event was attended by such large companies as "Sistemniye Technologies", "Foranks", "EPAM sistemz", "Sinesis", "Ozon Koncalting", "Itrazishen", "Softklub", "STXM", "MIXST", "YERPBEL".

The event resulted in the signing of a cooperation agreement between the Minsk company Sistemnie Technologies and the Baku company Ultra on the supply of information technologies for the banking sector to Azerbaijan [4]. Another important agreement on cooperation in the field of information and communication technologies was signed between the Rector of the Belarusian State University of Informatics and Radioelectronics Mikhail Batura and the Rector of the Azerbaijan Technical University Khavar Mammadov. Participant of the event, General Director of the innovation association "ST Qruppa" Alexander Mukovozchik, reporting on the prospects of joint activities of Azerbaijan

with three financial institutions, noted that the signed agreements will accelerate the movement of Belarusian services in the Azerbaijani market. During the bilateral meeting, Minister Abbasov stressed the need to create an analogue of the High-Tech Park in Belarus in Azerbaijan.

The fourth Belarusian-Azerbaijani business Forum in the field of high technologies and telecommunications, held in May 2018 in Minsk, was organized as part of the XXIV International Forum, where more than 100 exhibitors from more than 20 countries were represented. The Azerbaijani delegation at the exhibition was headed by the Director of the Department of Science, Technology and Information Development of the Ministry of Transport, Communications and High Technologies Rashad Azizov. Azerbaijan's achievements in the field of ICT, the presentation at the exhibition "TIBO-2018" in Minsk testify to the next stage of Azerbaijani-Belarusian cooperation in this field. The visitors of the national pavilion were given the opportunity to get acquainted with such important projects as "Creation of regional innovation zones", "Achievements in the field of space industry", "Creation of electronic government". The visit of the Minister of Communications and Informatization of the Republic of Belarus Sergey Popkov to the Azerbaijani pavilion means that Belarus attaches great importance to cooperation with Azerbaijan in the field of ICT. It is worth noting that the THIBAUULT Forum is included in the list of events held annually in Belarus, and Azerbaijan has been a regular participant of this event for 10 years. The structure of the exhibition highlights a number of technical areas, including "National Information Structure", "Digital Economy", "Mobile Technologies", "Electronic Government", "Robotics" and other important topics. The forum "Tibo" is attended by the world's leading manufacturers of telecommunications equipment, hardware, software, as well as mobile and fixed-line operators, manufacturers and suppliers of high-tech products, manufacturers of security systems and many other companies offering services in this field. The participation of more than 30 thousand specialists from all over the world in the forum is a favorable opportunity for establishing and developing interstate cooperation in this field [10]. The organization of such forums and meetings in the field of ICT is important because experts, heads of government agencies and business communities from around the world take part in business events, global trends in the development of ICT are analyzed, as well as their use in various fields of activity.

In the modern world, cybercrime is considered an important problem and is of concern. The leadership of the Republic of Azerbaijan makes important decisions on protection against cybercrime. In the legislation of Azerbaijan, both criminal and administrative procedural codes, there are articles concerning information technologies [1]. In November 2021, a conference organized in Baku entitled "Cybercrime is the most dangerous crime of the XXI century" testifies to Azerbaijan's readiness to fight cybercrime. The conference was attended by representatives of Great Britain, Belarus,

Albania, Moldova, Iran, Luxembourg, Georgia, Macedonia, as well as a number of other countries, representatives of the leadership of the Council of Europe. Azerbaijan cooperates with various countries in the fight against cybercrime, and since 2010 has joined the European Convention on Combating Cybercrime. Azerbaijani-Belarusian cooperation in the fight against cybercrime demands joint actions against threats to the modern world, in the fight against Internet crimes, as well as to ensure information security. In this direction, the Republic of Belarus and the Republic of Azerbaijan have declared a partnership. It is no coincidence that in November 2021, the Chairman of the Investigative Committee of the Republic of Belarus, Dmitriy Gara, in an interview with journalists, announced the further strengthening of cooperation with Azerbaijan in the field of cybercrime prevention and combating cybercrime. D. Gara noted that in this area Belarus is interested in further strengthening cooperation with the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Azerbaijan, in investigating specific criminal cases [4].

Conclusions The result of the last 20 years of the twentieth century has shown that information and communication technologies have become an important factor giving impetus to the development of society. An indisputable fact is the penetration of ICT into state structures and institutions of civil society, in the economic and social spheres, in the sphere of education and culture, in the whole way of life of people as a whole. Many developed and developing countries enjoy the benefits of information and communication technologies, it cannot be denied that the path to an information society is the future of humanity.

The introduction of ICT is the main indicator of the intellectual and scientific potential of each country, and also testifies to the transparency of public administration and the development of democracy. World experience confirms that the use of ICT serves the comprehensive development of the country and is one of the important tools for solving socio-economic problems of the population. In recent years, positive steps have been taken in the Republic of Azerbaijan and valuable achievements have been achieved in the use of information and communication technologies. The development of the ICT sector, cooperation with leading countries in this area is considered one of the priorities of state policy. The creation of an information society in Azerbaijan in the XXI century indicates that the sphere of information and communication technologies occupies a key place after the oil industry. It is an indisputable fact that the importance of ICT at present and in the future will appear in the foreground, will give a powerful impetus to the comprehensive development of the country. The interest in the development of this sphere in Azerbaijan is also reflected in the country's foreign economic policy, cooperation with Belarus, which has achieved success in the field of ICT, is of particular importance. The Republic of Belarus is actively developing its information infrastructure, being located at the junction of transport and information flows of the European continent, the country successfully uses its advantageous geographical position. The

digital transformation of the economy and the widespread introduction of innovations is one of the key factors ensuring the sustainable development of the country. We can say that Belarus is a leader in the CIS in the introduction of information and communication technologies. The development in the information and communication sphere is more significant compared to other sectors of the Belarusian economy. Taking all this into account, we can assess how important the cooperation of the Republic of Azerbaijan with the Republic of Belarus in the field of ICT is, the positive impact of the introduction of the Belarusian experience in Azerbaijan on economic and social life, as well as on improving the welfare of the people. Cooperation between Azerbaijan and Belarus in the field of ICT has a high potential. Countries are interested in creating zonal technologies and this has extraordinary prospects. After gaining independence, for more than 30 years, bilateral cooperation between Azerbaijan and Belarus has traditionally continued, Belarus, sharing advanced technologies, has a positive impact on strengthening the industrial, production and export potential of Azerbaijanis.

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